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TREATMENT-AND-PROPHYLACTIC COMPLEX AT THE STAGES OF PROSTHETICS WITH NON-REMOVABLE ORTHOPEDIC STRUCTURES

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Abstract

Patients who used the recommendations of an orthopedist on the 4th day showed a complete absence of pain, bleeding edema and hyperemia. times faster, the hygiene indicator stably remained in the “good” interval, while in the control group the state of hygiene worsened somewhat and the “satisfactory” hygiene interval returned.

Keywords: periodontium, fixed orthopedic structures, individual oral hygiene, Sensadin therapeutic and prophylactic agents, LISTERINE® rinse

As practice has shown, in the case of partial absence of teeth, preference is given to fixed bridge structures [6]. However, the process of manufacturing non-removable orthopedic structures has its own characteristics, which will determine the preservation of the viability of the pulp, the state of periodontal tissues, retention and fixation of the prosthesis, service life, and most importantly, its aesthetic appearance [5].

One of the features of the preparation of hard tissues of the tooth for fixed orthopedic structures is the creation of a cervical ledge, especially when prosthetics of the anterior group of teeth. [3]. The ledge should ensure a smooth transition of the artificial crown to the root of the tooth and prevent injury to the edge of the mucous membrane and the intergingival papilla [1]. However, excessive grinding of hard tissues with the creation of an excessive taper of the side walls leads to trauma to the pulp and the marginal periodontium, which in the future worsens the fixation of the finished prosthesis.

The injury can be caused by a gum retraction procedure. Gingival retraction is a procedure for expanding the gingival sulcus and is necessary to obtain high-quality two-layer impressions, although gum retraction is also carried out to protect the marginal periodontium

from mechanical injury by future fixed structures. In one case or another, the retraction procedure itself leads to periodontal injury [2]. Thus, trauma to the gums during preparation and retraction is inevitable, since the quality of the future fixed orthopedic structure and the period of its use depend on these manipulations. , And the probability of occurrence of gum recession processes after a certain period of time is quite high. To prevent the development of inflammatory changes in the marginal periodontium in the area of odontopreparation, it is important to eliminate local irritating factors, to conduct high-quality professional and individual oral hygiene (IHPR). This is due to the fact that after the preparation and fixation of temporary crowns, high-quality toothbrushing in this area becomes impossible, since it causes sharp pain, and the presence of pathogenic microorganisms will aggravate the situation and aggravate the inflammatory process. orthopedic structures will be different in each case [4]. When using dental floss inserted under the edge of the crown, it is necessary to make circular movements with the floss, which contributes to a better elimination of food debris, however, the use of super floss and brushes is much more effective. After that, it is mandatory to use oral

baths with rinse aid [7]. Individual oral hygiene should consist of the following mandatory steps:

- cleaning of the outer part of the bridge prosthesis - the actual crowns and the body of the structure
- cleaning of the internal surface of the bridge prosthesis - internal (hidden) spaces around the artificial crowns and the internal surface of the body of the prosthesis (flushing space) to avoid the formation of bedsores under them.

For these purposes, a special thread is produced, which the patient can easily stretch between the gums and the body of the bridge [8]. Therapeutic and prophylactic agents used for IHPR during prosthetics must meet certain requirements. So, the means used actually after the first stage of prosthetics and until the full adaptation of periodontal tissues should have a pronounced antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and keratoplastic effect.

Deodorizing and refreshing properties. Therefore, the issues of prevention of complications that occur in periodontal tissues during and after prosthetics with fixed structures, as well as the features of individual oral hygiene and the choice of therapeutic and prophylactic agents remain relevant.

The purpose of the study is to increase the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment and prevention of complications by developing an algorithm for individual oral hygiene at the stages of prosthetics with fixed structures.

Materials and research methods. Orthopedic treatment was carried out in 42 patients aged 26–8 years with defects in the dentition. 112 abutment vital teeth were prepared for fixed combined constructions.

Patients were trained in the hygienic regimen and the ability to control it, as well as in the hygienic care of orthopedic structures. Particular attention was focused on areas that require increased attention - the contact surfaces of the prosthesis with adjacent teeth, the surfaces of the intermediate part adjacent to the gums and the flushing zone in the area of the intermediate part of the bridge.

To study the effectiveness of the proposed complex of individual oral hygiene, all patients were divided into two groups: Main group - 25 patients (61 supporting teeth). Individual oral hygiene was carried out according to this scheme for an average of two weeks. In the morning and in the evening:

- toothpaste "Sensadin Aktiv" (2–3 min.);
- interdental hygiene "dental floss" and brushes "Interdental"; During the day and after each meal:
- LISTERINE® rinses as part of complex care help remove plaque, bacteria and their metabolic products from hard-to-reach areas of the oral cavity.

As a result, the concentration of microorganisms decreases, the tooth receives additional protection, the risk of inflammation and bleeding of the gums decreases, and bad breath is eliminated.

Stage II: after fixing the permanent structure - within four weeks.

Morning and evening: toothpaste "Sensadin-Health of gums" (2-3 min.); "Sensadin with fluoride for sensitive teeth" (2-3min)

- toothbrush (medium type)
- interdental hygiene "dental floss" and brushes "Interdental".
- LISTERINE® line rinses

Control group - 17 patients (51 abutment teeth), patients chose personal oral hygiene products on their own.

Results of the study In patients of the main group on the third day after preparation and use of the doctor's recommendations, there was a significant improvement in the condition of the marginal periodontium and a complete absence of pain, on the 5th day - objectively: there is no bleeding, swelling and hyperemia. A follow-up examination after three months showed that in patients who were trained in the hygiene regimen and used Sensadin and LISTERINE® rinse, the hygiene index remained stable in the "good" interval, while in the control group the hygiene condition worsened slightly. Individual oral hygiene at the stages of prosthetics with fixed orthopedic structures is important and has its own characteristics. In patients who were trained in the features of the hygienic regime in the presence of non-removable orthopedic structures and used therapeutic and prophylactic agents prescribed by the doctor, the condition of the marginal periodontium returned to normal two times faster than in patients who independently selected personal oral hygiene products.

Therapeutic and hygienic complex for individual oral hygiene using Sensadin and LISTERINE® rinse accelerated the normalization of the state of injured tissues of the marginal periodontium, which contributed to their speedy adaptation to fixed orthopedic structures and the prevention of periodontitis.

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